

Estimate the Level of FSH, LH and Its Relation with AMH in Females with PCOS and Healthy Control GroupAnshul Mohan Kala¹, Nimisha Gupta², Astha Chamoli³, Tariq Masood⁴, Arindam Basu⁵¹Assistant Professor, Shri Guru Ram Rai Institute of Medical and Health Sciences, Dehradun, Uttarakhand-248001²Assistant Professor, Government Doon Medical College, Dehradun Uttarakhand-248001³Assistant Professor, Rajshree Medical Research Institute, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh -243501⁴Professor and Head, Shri Guru Ram Rai Institute of Medical and Health Sciences, Dehradun, Uttarakhand-248001⁵Associate Professor, Shri Guru Ram Rai Institute of Medical and Health Sciences, Dehradun, Uttarakhand-248001

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Abstract:

Polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) is a prevalent endocrine disorder affecting 6-8% of women worldwide, associated with reproductive dysfunction, metabolic disturbances, and increased cardiovascular risk. This study aimed to evaluate the serum levels of follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), luteinizing hormone (LH), and anti-Mullerian hormone (AMH) in PCOS patients compared to healthy controls. A cross-sectional study was conducted with 116 women (76 with PCOS and 40 controls) aged 15-35 years, diagnosed using the Rotterdam criteria. The results demonstrated significantly higher levels of LH (12.449 ± 4.86 mIU/ml) and AMH (6.812 ± 3.32 ng/ml) in PCOS patients compared to controls (LH: 5.436 ± 4.32 mIU/ml; AMH: 2.479 ± 2.30 ng/ml), while FSH levels were lower in PCOS patients (5.872 ± 1.92 mIU/ml) versus controls (7.153 ± 3.15 mIU/ml). A reversal in the LH/FSH ratio was observed in PCOS, suggesting gonadotropin dysregulation. Elevated AMH levels highlight its diagnostic potential for PCOS, independent of the menstrual cycle. In conclusion, the altered hormonal profiles in PCOS patients support the utility of AMH as a diagnostic marker, alongside disruptions in LH and FSH levels, offering insights into PCOS pathophysiology and diagnosis.

Keywords: Polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS), anti-Mullerian hormone (AMH), luteinizing hormone (LH), follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), Rotterdam criteria, hormonal imbalance, diagnosis.

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Introduction

Polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) is the most common endocrine disorder in women, as many as one in seven women may be living with it. The disorder that eventually would be known as the polycystic ovary (or ovarian) syndrome (PCOS) was initially described by STEIN and LEVNTAL in 1935 [1]

New Data suggest that it affects between 6% and 8% of women worldwide, using the National institute of Health (NIH) 1990 criteria [2]

Clinically, diagnosing a woman as having PCOS implies an increased risk for infertility, dysfunctional bleeding, endometrial carcinoma, obesity, type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM), dyslipidemia, hypertension, and possibly cardiovascular disease (CVD).[3] The functional integrity of hypothalamic pituitary ovarian axis, via endometrium are responsible for normal

reproductive function in female, leading to synchronized release of gonadotropins and steroidal hormones essential for ovulation events leading to conception.[4]

Rotterdam criteria. A task force sponsored by the European Society of Human Reproduction and Embryology (ESHRE) and the American Society for Reproduction Medicine (ASRM) met in Rotterdam, The Netherlands, in 2003 to review the available data and proposed a revision to the 1990 NIH diagnostic paradigm, hence the inception of the Rotterdam criteria. More recently, in 2009, [5]

AMH Anti-Mullerian hormone (AMH) has recently been proposed as a parameter to replace ultrasonographic assessment of PCO morphology, with specificity and sensitivity of 97.1 and 94.6% when using the Rotterdam criteria, or 97.5% using the NIH criteria.[6] FSH is synthesized and

secreted by the gonadotropic cells of the anterior pituitary gland and regulates the development, growth, pubertal maturation, and reproductive processes of the body. FSH and luteinizing hormone (LH) work together in the reproductive system. [7] LH (luteinizing hormone): also known as lutropin is a hormone produced by anterior Pituitary. It is a glycoprotein hormone having subunits. The alpha subunit is like those of FSH, hCG, and TSH In females: ovulation, maintaining of corpus luteum and secretion of progesterone. [7]

The aim of this study is to estimate the change in levels of serum FSH, LH, and AMH in women with PCOS and to compare these levels with normal healthy controls.

Materials and Method

This hospital-based cross-sectional study was conducted at the Out-Patient Department of Gynecology, SGR Institute of Medical and Health Sciences, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, from August 2016 to September 2017. A total of 116 women, including 76 PCOS cases and 40 healthy controls, aged 15-35 years with normal menstrual cycles, were randomly selected for the study.

PCOS was diagnosed using the Rotterdam Criteria, which included the presence of oligomenorrhea (OA), hyperandrogenism (HA), and polycystic ovarian morphology (PCOM). Additionally, AMH

was introduced as a fourth parameter, and its inclusion increased diagnostic sensitivity.

Exclusion criteria included women younger than 15 or older than 35, as well as those with a history of chronic diseases such as diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular disease, or tuberculosis.

Blood samples were collected on the 2nd or 3rd day of the menstrual cycle, and the serum levels of FSH, LH, and AMH were measured using the fully automated VITROS 5600 system.

Result

Chart 1. the age of 21-25 the total number of case was 26.31 % and control group was 25 %.the age from 25-35 the total number of case was 71.05 %and control group was 75 %.

Table 1. The serum levels of LH were significantly much higher in PCOS females 12.449±4.86±0.55 mIU/ml as compared to normal controls 5.436±4.32±0.68 mIU/ml. Serum AMH levels were also found to be higher 6.812±3.32±0.38 ng/ml as compared to normal control2.479±2.30±0.36 ng/ml.

The serum levels of FSH were found to be lower in PCOS females 5.872±1.92±0.22 mIU/ml as compared to normal controls. We also found a reversal in LH: FSH ratio7.153±3.15±0.50 mIU/ml.

Chart 1: Percentage of Total No. of Cases & Control group

Table 1: Hormonal Assays in PCOS Cases & Control groups

Parameter	Cases (mean±SD±SE)	Control (mean±SD±SE)	t-value	p-value	Significance
FSH	5.872±1.92±0.22	7.153±3.15±0.50	-2.716	0.0076	Significant
LH	12.449±4.86±0.55	5.436±4.32±0.68	7.732	<0.0001	Highly Significant
AMH	6.812±3.32±0.38	2.479±2.30±0.36	0.588	<0.0001	Highly Significant

Diagonal segments are produced by ties.

Chart 2: FSH ROC Curve/Test/AUC=0.353

The area under the curve (AUC) was 0.353 (95% CI .246 -.459). Sensitivity= True Positive, Specificity= False Positive

Chart 3: LH ROC Curve/Test/AUC=0.926

The area under the curve (AUC) was 0.926 (95% CI 0.856-0.997). Sensitivity= True Positive Rate, 1-Specificity= False Positive Rate

Chart 4: AMH ROC Curve/Test/AUC=0.882

The area under the curve (AUC) was 0.882 (95% CI 0.815-0.949). Sensitivity= True Positive Rate, 1-Specificity= False Positive Rate

Discussion

Low FSH Disordered FSH secretion is postulated as a possible mechanism for ovulatory dysfunction in PCOS; indeed, levels of FSH are slightly lower in women with PCOS and do not show intercycle rise in the normal menstrual cycle [8, 9, 10]. In our study FSH, was $5.76 \pm 1.95 \pm 0.32$ in PCOS patient as compared to $6.95 \pm 3.20 \pm 0.69$ in normal controls. Luteinizing Hormone (LH): The raised serum LH is often found in women with PCOS. As postulated to play a mechanistic role in androgen excess of PCOS [11, 12, 13]. We found significant raised LH, $12.19 \pm 6.94 \pm 0.81$ in 76 patients in comparison $5.44 \pm 4.39 \pm 0.94$ (Mean \pm SD \pm SE) in normal control (40 patients).

Raised AMH, in PCOS: AMH circulates at significantly higher levels in women with anovulatory PCOS has led to a hypothesis that AMH excess may be contributory to anovulation PCOS. In a case control study conducted by Budi Wiweko, Mila Maidarti, et al. (2011) found that AMH serum levels were significantly higher in PCOS patient than in controls. [14]

In the present study AMH was $(6.59 \pm 3.38 \pm 0.56)$ in PCOS patients compared with normal controls $(2.48 \pm 2.33 \pm 0.50)$. This study showed that AMH could be used as an alternative diagnostic tool in PCOS patients. Pigny et al. found that the specificity and sensitivity of serum AMH measurement reached 92 and 67 %, respectively

[15]. Lin et al. obtained the cutoff AMH level of 7.3 ng/mL, giving 76 % specificity 76 % and 70 % sensitivity to predict PCOS. We obtained a cutoff value of 4.45 ng/mL, lower than the findings of Lin et al [16].

Our study supports the notion that AMH is not only a diagnostic marker but also a potential prognostic tool for PCOS. Dewailly et al. (2014) posited that AMH could be used to assess the severity of ovarian dysfunction and predict the likelihood of ovulatory disturbances in women with PCOS. The stability of AMH levels across the menstrual cycle and its independence from hormonal influences make it a reliable biomarker for both diagnosis and disease progression monitoring. [17]

The elevated AMH levels observed in our study are in line with findings from Laven et al. (2004), [18] who demonstrated that women with PCOS exhibit increased ovarian reserve due to the excessive recruitment of small antral follicles.

These follicles secrete AMH, leading to higher circulating levels compared to healthy controls. Our findings also align with those of Eilertsen et al. (2012), who found that AMH levels are highly sensitive and specific for PCOS diagnosis. [19] Polycystic ovary (63.4%). However, the mean level of AMH was highest in the phenotypes of anovulation, polycystic ovaries and hyperandrogenism (11.1 ng/ml) [20].

The level of AMH circulating in the blood is not affected by the menstrual cycle nor altered during the use of oral contraceptives, therefore it can be

used as a potential biological marker for PCO or PCOS (21).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the results of this study underscore the importance of using the Rotterdam Criteria for diagnosing PCOS, with a special emphasis on incorporating AMH as an additional diagnostic tool. Elevated AMH levels in PCOS patients reflect the increased follicular activity and serve as a reliable marker for ovarian dysfunction.

AMH offers a stable, cycle-independent biomarker that can enhance the accuracy of PCOS diagnosis, particularly when used in conjunction with traditional parameters like LH and FSH.

Given the increasing prevalence of PCOS and its associated metabolic and reproductive complications, identifying more accurate diagnostic tools is crucial for early intervention and management.

This study contributes to the growing body of evidence supporting AMH's role in PCOS diagnosis and highlights the need for further research into its potential prognostic value in predicting long-term outcomes for women with PCOS.

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